

Effect of azolla and inorganic N on rice.^a Coimbatore, India, 1983-84

Treatment ^b	1983 wet season					1983-84 dry season				
	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Control (no N)	6.4 d	245 d	69 d	2.5 d	4.0 d	6.1 d	212 d	63 d	2.3 d	4.0 d
100 kg N-PU	13.4 b	502 b	91 b	5.9 b	7.7 b	13.1 b	483 b	83 bc	5.5 b	7.6 b
25 kg N-azolla+ 75 kg N-PU	11.0 c	413 c	88 c	5.0 c	6.4 c	10.7 c	397 c	80 c	4.5 c	6.2 c
100 kg N-USG	15.2 a	618 a	100 a	7.0 a	9.0 a	14.8 a	598 a	87 ab	6.5 a	8.4 a
25 kg N-azolla + 75 kg N-USG	15.1 a	565 a	100 a	7.0 a	8.9 a	14.6 a	560 a	89 a	6.4 a	8.4 a

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bN rate = 100 kg/ha.

Effect of cultivation method on the rice crop and the mechanical impediment of Vertisols

B.L. Ganjir and R.P. Rajput, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, J.N. Agricultural University, Jabalpur 482004, M.P., India

Puddling for transplanted rice facilitates transplanting, maintenance of submergence, and weed control. But in Vertisols, with low infiltration rates, puddling disturbs the soil physical condition and creates problems for field preparation of dry season wheat.

We studied the influence of different cultivation methods on the rice crop and soil mechanical impediment. Treatments — direct drilling (DD), direct transplanting (DT), bullock puddling (BP), and tractor puddling (TP) — were in a randomized block design with four

Table 1. Effect of puddling on penetration force. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Depth (m)	Penetration force (kg/cm ²)	
		Tillering stage	Milk stage
Direct drilling	5	1.49	4.61
	10	4.93	6.26
	15	6.49	7.36
Direct transplanting	5	2.15	4.85
	10	5.30	6.24
	15	6.39	7.49
Bullock puddling	5	1.37	2.74
	10	3.31	6.01
	15	4.37	7.35
Tractor puddling	5	1.02	2.80
	10	4.47	6.18
	15	6.02	7.43

Table 2. Effect of method of cultivation on growth and yield of paddy. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Plant height (cm)	Tillers/Plant	Panicle length (cm)
	Grain	Straw			
Direct drilling	4.2	10.6	76.8	6.3	20.8
Direct transplanting	3.3	8.4	75.6	6.4	21.2
Bullock puddling	3.7	9.2	77.8	6.4	21.2
Tractor puddling	3.4	9.4	72.0	6.3	21.3
CD at 0.05	0.7	1.5	ns	ns	no
cv (%)	28	19	—	—	—

replications. Rice variety Ratna was sown 7 Nov 1985. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha.

Plant height, tiller numbers, panicle length, and grain and straw yields were recorded. Penetration force at tillering and milk stages was measured by penetrometer.

DD gave the highest mechanical impediment (MI), and TP the lowest, irrespective of growth stage (Table 1). The increased magnitude of MI at the

milk stage was attributed to reduced moisture content.

Tillers/ plant, plant height, and panicle length did not differ significantly (Table 2). DD gave the significantly highest grain and straw yield. The differences among DT, BP, and TP were not significant. A similar trend was found with straw yield.

Reduced yield due to puddling is attributed to deterioration of physical conditions of the soil. □

Efficiency of nitrogen fertilizers and a nitrification inhibitor

Yadvinder-Singh, Bijay-Singh, and M.S. Maskina, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

We studied the relative efficiency of urea, ammonium sulfate, and potassium nitrate during 1986 kharif (Jun-Sep). Nitrification inhibitor 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (ATC) was applied at 5% by weight of urea. To restrict NH₃ volatilization, urea-nitrification inhibitor and urea alone treatments were applied

in bands (3 cm below surface) between the rows. N at 110 kg/ha was applied in 3 equal splits: 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting with no standing water.

Soil of the experimental field was Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.23% organic C, 7 kg Olsen's P/ha and 71 kg ammonium acetate extractable K/ha. Soil percolation rate was about 6 mm/h. Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Six-week-old seedlings of rice variety PR106 were transplanted the third week of June. □

Urea and ammonium sulfate topdressed in three equal splits did not differ significantly (see table). Band application slightly increased grain yield and N uptake over topdressing. Additional benefit with band placement was probably due to the low rate of nitrification.

Application of ATC, a water-soluble chemical recommended for nitrification inhibition, did not influence yield and N uptake of rice, even at higher rates. This may be due to ineffective coating and leaching of the chemical from the bands. Potassium nitrate was the most

Influence of N source and a nitrification inhibitor (ATC) on yield and N uptake of wetland rice. Ludhiana (Punjab), India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)
	Grain	Straw		
Ammonium sulfate (topdressed)	7.6	8.8	124.5	11.8
Urea (topdressed)	7.2	8.8	113.2	61.5
Potassium nitrate (topdressed)	4.8	6.3	80.6	37.9
Urea (banded)	7.8	9.2	122.6	76.1
Urea + ATC (banded)	7.7	9.3	119.8	13.5
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.6	0.8	5.4	—
Control (no N)	2.5	3.5	38.9	—

inefficient N source. Recovery of N from potassium nitrate was about half that from ammonium sulfate and urea. □

Effect of plant density and fertilization on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency

M.S. Zia, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

We studied fertilizer efficiency at different N P levels and different plant densities, with IR6 as the test variety.

Plant density and NP level significantly affected yield (see table). The highest yield was at 20- × 20-cm spacing (250,000 hills/ha) and the lowest at 40- × 25-cm spacing (100,000 hills/ha). The highest yield was with

Effect of plant density and fertilizer level on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency. Muridke, Pakistan.

Spacing (cm)	Plant density (hills/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level				Mean for plant density ^a (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg rice/kg N) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level			Mean for plant density (kg rice/kg N)
		0-60	60-60	90-60	120-60		60-60	90-60	120-60	
40 × 25	100,000	3.2	5.7	5.9	6.3	5.2 c	42	30	26	33
25 × 25	160,000	3.2	6.0	6.1	6.7	5.5 b	44	32	28	35
20 × 25	200,000	3.5	6.2	6.4	6.9	5.7 ab	45	33	29	36
20 × 20	250,000	3.7	6.4	6.7	7.2	6.0 a	46	34	29	36
Mean for fertilizer ^a		3.4 c	6.1 b	6.3 b	6.8 a		44	32	28	

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other.

120-26 kg NP/ha.

Fertilizer efficiency was lowest at the highest level of fertilization, increasing

gradually with decreased fertilizer.

Fertilizer efficiency was highest at higher plant densities. □

Effect of method of applying *Azospirillum brasilense* on rice yield

G. Gopalaswamy and P. Vidhyasekaran, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

Azospirillum brasilense Tarrand *et al.* fixes atmospheric N in soil. We studied methods of applying bacterium to increase yield. Peat-based *A. brasilense* inoculum (6 kg/ha) containing 10⁸ bacteria/g of peat soil was used for all treatments.

For seed treatment, 60 kg of seeds were soaked for 24 h in 60 liters water containing 6 kg peat-based inoculum. The seeds were allowed to sprout, then sown in the nursery. For seedling treatment, seedling roots were dipped in

Method of application of *Azospirillum* on rice yield. TNRRI, Aduthurai, India.

<i>Azospirillum</i> application method	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Seed	87	8	8.0	4.9
Seedling	86	7	1.2	4.8
Soil	86	7	1.5	4.6
Seed + seedling	88	7	8.8	5.6
Seed + soil	89	7	1.4	4.8
Seedling + soil	86	7	8.3	5.5
Seed + seedling + soil	89	8	9.3	6.5
Uninoculated (control)	84	6	6.3	4.4
CD	3	1	1.4	1.0

400 liters water containing 6 kg inoculum for 20 min and transplanted. Soil application of the bacterium was done by mixing 6 kg inoculum with 15 kg sand and broadcasting in the main field before transplanting. Inoculum also

was split into two doses and given as seed + seedling treatment or seed + soil treatment or seedling + soil treatment. In the last treatment, inoculum was split into three doses and given as seed + seedling + soil treatment.